

Impact Factor: 5.186

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Special Issue 1

2023

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

1 МАХСУС СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

ТОШКЕНТ-2023

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№SI-1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2023-SI-1>

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Мадазимов Мадамин Муминович
Ректор Андижанского Государственного
медицинского института, д.м.н., профессор
кафедры факультетской и госпитальной
хирургии

Тахририят раиси:
Председатель редакционной коллегии:
Chairman of the editorial Board:

Алексеев Андрей Анатольевич
Директор ожогового центра НМИЦ хирургии
им. В.Вишневского, главный комбустиолог
Министерства здравоохранения России, д.м.н.,
профессор.

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Салахиддинов Камалиддин Зухриддинович
доцент, д.м.н. кафедры факультетской и
госпитальной хирургии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Хегай Любовь Николаевна
доцент, к.м.н., начальник отдела по координации
деятельности грантов Межвузовской научно-
исследовательской лаборатории Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Досина Маргарита Олеговна
в.н.с. ГНУ "Институт физиологии Национальной
академии наук Беларуси", к.б.н., председатель
Совета молодых ученых Отделения медицинских
наук НАН Беларуси

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Ниязова Зебинисо Анваровна
PhD кафедры офтальмологии, детской
офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ ТАХРИРИЙ МАСЛАХАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ EDITORIAL BOARD OF THE UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Хужамбердиев Мамазоир Ахмедович

д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной терапии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Привалова Ирина Леонидовна

д.б.н., профессор кафедры нормальной физиологии Курского государственного медицинского университета,
заведующая лабораторией физиологии висцеральных систем НИИ физиологии (Курск)

Гаврилова Елена Анатольевна

д.м.н., профессор, заведующая кафедрой лечебной физкультуры и спортивной медицины Северо-западного
государственного медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Чурганов Олег Анатольевич

д.п.н., профессор кафедры ЛФК и спортивной медицины Северо-Западного государственного
медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Салахиддинов Зухриддин Салахиддинович

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой ВОП №1, Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Рябчиков Денис Анатольевич

д.м.н., в.н.с. онкологического отделения хирургических методов лечения ФГБУ "НМИЦ
онкологии им. Н.Н. Блохина" Минздрава России

Гулямов Суръат Саидвалиевич

д.м.н., профессор кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, стоматологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Тереза Магалхайз
профессор, заведующая кафедрой Судебной медицины государственного университета Порту (Португалия)

Юлдашев Илхом Рузиевич
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой Аллергологии, иммунологии, микробиологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Хамраев Абдурашид Журакулович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной детской хирургии, Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Эрматов Низом Жумакулович
д.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой гигиены детей и подростков и гигиены питания Ташкентской медицинской академии

Рузиев Шерзод Ибодуллаевич
д.м.н., доцент кафедры судебной медицины и медицинского права Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Якубова Олтиной Абдуганиевна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии, неонатологии факультета повышения квалификации и переподготовки врачей Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Бабич Светлана Михайловна
доцент, заведующая кафедрой социальной гигиены Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Сабирова Рихси Абдукадировна
д.м.н., профессор кафедры медицинской и биологической химии Ташкентской медицинской академии

Цеомашко Наталья Евгеньевна
д.б.н., с.н.с., заведующая отделом медико-генетических исследований МНИЛ Ташкентской медицинской академии

Хамраева Лола Салимовна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманходжаева Адиба Амирсаидовна
доцент, к.м.н., заведующая кафедрой Народной медицины, реабилитологии и физической культуры Ташкентской медицинской академии

Тухтаева Нигора Хасановна
DSc, доцент кафедры пропедевтики внутренних болезней № 2, Ташкентской медицинской академии.

Шарипова Фарида Камилевна
к.м.н., доцент кафедры психиатрии, наркологии и детской психиатрии, медицинской психологии, психотерапии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бузруков Батир Тулкунович
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Туйчиев Галибжан Урмонжонович
к.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой детской хирургии, детской анестезиологии-реаниматологии с курсом
офтальмологии и стоматологии факультета усовершенствования и переподготовки врачей АГМИ

Маматхужаева Гулнора Нажмитдиновна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Офтальмологии Андижанского Государственного медицинского института

Каримова Зиёда Кушбаевна
доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Аллергологии, клинической иммунологии, микробиологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Саидходжаева Саида Набиевна
доцент, Phd кафедры неврологии, детской неврологии и медицинской генетики Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Зуфарова Зухра Хабибуллаевна
доцент, к.ф.н. кафедры промышленной технологии лекарственных средств Ташкентского фармацевтического института

Ибрагимова Марина Фёдоровна
PhD, ассистент кафедры N1 педиатрии и неонатологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета.

Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна
PhD кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, детской стоматологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хўршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Primov F.Sh., Akilov B.B., Kurbonov J.R., Djuraev J.A. EVOLUTION OF VIEWS AND MODERN TRENDS IN ENDOVISUAL SURGICAL TREATMENT FOR URGENT ABDOMINAL PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN.....	7
2. Pulatova Sh.Kh. A NEW APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE.....	14
3. Pulatova Sh.Kh., Tasheva F.A. A NEW APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY WITH HEART FAILURE.....	20
4. Khamroev E.E., Pulatova Sh.Kh. THE CHOICE OF MEDICINAL PRODUCTS FOR CHRONIC HEART FAILURE OF VARIOUS GENESIS IN THE ELDERLY.....	26
5. Rasulova Nodira Alisherovna, Khojaeva Nikzan Nazarbekovna INFLUENCE OF 25(OH)D ON THE CAUSES OF RICKETS IN CHILDREN.....	34
6. Natalya Vladimirovna Voronina, Matluba Shamtsudinova SANITARY AND HYGIENIC MONITORING OF PESTICIDE POLLUTION OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	39
7. Rasulova Nadira Alisherovna, Khakimova Sohiba Ziyadullayevna THE USE OF MUSIC THERAPY FOR THE CORRECTION OF PSYCHOSOMATIC DISORDERS IN CHILDREN.....	46
8. Abdieva Yulduz Atakulovna, Agzamova Gulnara Sunnatovna CHANGES IN THE CYTOKINE PROFILE IN PATIENTS WITH SILICOSIS IN COMBINATION WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION.....	50
9. Davlatova Dilrabo, Usmanova Shoirra THE ROLE OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES.....	57
10. Nozima Tokhirzhonovna Mavlyanova, Nazifa Valievna Agzamova CLINICAL AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS AND ITS POSSIBILITIES IN THE EVALUATION OF THE USE OF ANTIBACTERIAL DRUGS.....	64
11. Kamilov Khaydar, Usmanova Lazzat, Akhmadaliev N.N. DYNAMICS OF THE CYTOKINE PROFILE OF THE ORAL FLUID IN PATIENTS WITH SETTON'S APHTHOSIS.....	67
12. Mirzaev Husanjon, Rizaev Eler FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE AND FREQUENCY OF OCCURRENCE OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES AND ORAL MUCOSA IN PATIENTS SUFFERING FROM CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....	73

13. Mirzaev Husanjon, Rizaev Eler THE NATURE OF CHANGES IN BIOMARKERS OF KIDNEY DAMAGE IN SALIVA, BLOOD AND URINE IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS....	79
14. Davlatova Dilrabo, Usmanova Shaira ENDOTHELIAL CELL DYSFUNCTION BY CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION.....	85
15. Kamilov Kh.P., Kahharova D.J. HUMAN PAPILLOMA VIRUS AND ORAL MUCOSA LESIONS: INCREASED POTENTIAL OF MALIGNANT DEGENERATION.....	89
16. Rasulov A.B., Arifov S.S., Zufarov A.A. ON THE ISSUE OF HEARING SCREENING AMONG PREMATURE NEWBORNS.....	94
17. Yusupova Shahnoza EFFICIENCY OF IMIQUIMOD IN TREATMENT OF CONDYLOMA ACUMINATA.....	100

ISSN: 2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

Primov F.Sh.,
Akilov B.B.,
Kurbonov J.R.,
Djuraev J.A.

Center for the Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical Workers
Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care

EVOLUTION OF VIEWS AND MODERN TRENDS IN ENDOVISUAL SURGICAL TREATMENT FOR URGENT ABDOMINAL PATHOLOGY IN CHILDREN

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7782899>

ABSTRACT

The article highlights the development of laparoscopic surgery in pediatrics, the current state of this problem in surgical hospitals, the difficulties associated with the transition to minimally invasive surgical interventions in the provision of emergency surgical care for children. In case of complicated forms of appendicitis, foreign objects in the organs of the gastrointestinal tract, obstructive and strangulation obstruction of the small and large intestines, intussusception of intestinal loops in children, it is necessary to modernize and introduce laparoscopic technologies into surgical practice using tools for endovisual surgical treatment. Variants of possible risks when using laparoscopic access and ways to reduce them are analyzed, the advantages of this technique in comparison with open surgical interventions are noted, and its reliable cost-effectiveness is demonstrated.

Keywords: laparoscopic surgery, emergency surgery, obstructive intestinal obstruction, strangulation intestinal obstruction, appendicitis.

Примова Ф.Ш.,
Акилова Б.Б.,
Курбонов Ж.Р.,
Джураева Ж.А.

Центр развития профессиональной
квалификации медицинских работников
Республиканский научный центр
экстренной медицинской помощи

ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ ВЗГЛЯДОВ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ ЭНДОВИЗУАЛЬНОГО ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПРИ УРГЕНТНОЙ АБДОМИНАЛЬНОЙ ПАТОЛОГИИ У ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье освещены вопросы развития лапароскопической хирургии в педиатрии, современное состояние данной проблемы в хирургических стационарах, сложности, связанные с переходом на выполнение малоинвазивных хирургических вмешательств, при оказании экстренной

хирургической помощи детям. При осложненных формах аппендицита, инородных предметах в органах желудочно-кишечного тракта, обтурационной и strangуляционной непроходимости тонкого и толстого кишечника, инвагинации петель кишечника у детей необходимо модернизировать и внедрение в хирургическую практику лапароскопических технологий с применением инструментов эндовизуального хирургического лечения. Проанализированы варианты возможных рисков при использовании лапароскопического доступа и способы их уменьшения, отмечены преимущества данной методики по сравнению с открытыми оперативными вмешательствами, продемонстрирована ее достоверная экономическая эффективность.

Ключевые слова: лапароскопические операции, неотложная хирургия, обтурационной кишечной непроходимости, strangуляционной кишечной непроходимости, аппендицит.

**Primov F.Sh.,
Akilova B. B.,
Qurbonov J.R.
Djuraev J.A.**

Tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini oshirish markazi
Respublika shoshilinch tibbiy yordam ilmiy markazi

BOLALARDA SHOSHILINCH QORIN PATOLOGIYASI UCHUN ENDOVASKULAR JARROHLIK DAVOLASHDA QARASHLAR EVOLYUTSIYASI VA ZAMONAVIY TENDENTSIYALAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada pediatriyada Laparoskopik jarrohlikning rivojlanishi, jarrohlik shifoxonalarida ushbu muammoning hozirgi holati, bolalarga shoshilinch jarrohlik yordamini ko'rsatishda minimal invaziv jarrohlik aralashuvlarga o'tish bilan bog'liq qiyinchiliklar yoritilgan. Appenditsitning murakkab shakllari, oshqozon-ichak trakti organlarida begona narsalar, ingichka va yo'g'on ichaklarning obstruktiv va strangulyatsion obstruktiviyasi, bolalarda ichak qovuzloqlarining intussuscepsiyasi bo'lsa, endovizual jarrohlik davolash vositalaridan foydalangan holda Laparoskopik texnologiyalarni modernizatsiya qilish va jarrohlik amaliyotiga joriy etish zarur. Laparoskopik kirishni qo'llashda mumkin bo'lgan xavflarning variantlari va ularni kamaytirish usullari tahlil qilinadi, ushbu texnikaning ochiq jarrohlik aralashuvlarga nisbatan afzalliklari qayd etiladi va uning ishonchli iqtisodiy samaradorligi namoyish etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Laparoskopik jarrohlik, shoshilinch jarrohlik, obstruktiv ichak tutilishi, strangulyatsiya ichak tutilishi, appenditsit.

With complicated forms of appendicitis, foreign objects in the organs of the gastrointestinal tract, obturation and strangulation obstruction of the small and large intestines, intussusception of intestinal loops in children, it is necessary to modernize and introduce laparoscopic technologies into surgical practice using endovisual surgical treatment tools. Patients with intestinal intussusception belong to the segment of patients with appendicular peritonitis, the classification of which can also be considered from the standpoint of the effectiveness of endoscopic technologies [15]. However, to date, there is no fully formed classification of appendicular peritonitis that takes into account laparoscopic surgery [1,7].

The existing experience in the treatment of acute appendicitis in children, which exceeds one hundred years, indicates that significant changes and successes have been achieved by pediatric surgeons in this area. Due to the currently available technologies of modern medicine, namely various methods of surgical treatment of children with peritonitis, there is a positive dynamics of this category of patients in the postoperative period [4]. However, it should be noted that to date it has not been possible to eradicate the development of postoperative complications in patients with diffuse appendicular peritonitis [2]. At the same time, the prediction of the development of these

complications is difficult, respectively, the effect on the occurrence of the inflammatory process of the parietal peritoneum is minimal.

Currently, much has been studied and possible complications of laparoscopic operations have been described, and therefore, widely used measures have been developed to prevent their occurrence. Depending on the cause of complications that occur during surgery, complications are classified into 4 groups: anesthetic; complications that occur during surgical access; intraoperative and infectious [5,9].

Some complications associated with anesthesia develop due to the following factor - the occurrence of a disorder in the work of the cardiopulmonary system when applying carboxylperitoneum. The most important features of the anesthetic provision of laparoscopic surgical treatment of children is the performance of endotracheal anesthesia. The implementation of general anesthesia with the use of artificial lung ventilation, the implementation of muscle relaxation in full, which creates favorable conditions for surgeons both at the time of surgery and in the postoperative period, in order to prevent the development of complications, as well as the implementation of full and detailed monitoring at the time of surgery are mandatory and necessary conditions for anesthesia in any laparoscopic interventions, namely diagnostic and operative [28].

During the stage of performing operative access, the appearance and development of various complications is also possible. Their development occurs due to injury to the arteries and veins or organs of the abdominal cavity, or due to the introduction of extraperitoneal carbon dioxide. According to various authors, the frequency of damage to the large omentum, stomach, small and large intestines, liver, large arteries and veins, and other organs during abdominal puncture ranges from 0.1 to 2.2%; but more than 50% of these complications are due to the adhesive process [24]. It is noted that most contraindications are no longer considered as absolute, since there is the introduction of modern technologies, modernized instruments in surgical practice. It is obvious that with the correct determination of the prevalence of adhesions, the correctness of the choice of operative access, the use of specialized technical techniques and techniques allow laparoscopic surgery to be performed successfully in many patients with formed adhesions in the abdominal cavity. At the same time, with the help of laparoscopic interventions, it is possible to prevent the formation and formation of adhesions in the subsequent period [6,27].

With the help of such techniques as open laparoscopy, diagnostic laparoscopy with revision of the abdominal organs immediately after performing surgical access, it is possible to achieve the result that such complications will be eliminated in a timely manner or will not occur. Intraoperative complications during the operation are associated, respectively, with the surgical intervention itself, namely, the occurrence of bleeding, perforation of the hollow organ and others, as well as the electrocoagulation used cause the development of complications, but recently this issue remains debatable. It is believed that infection and contamination by microorganisms from the skin of trocar wounds is a rare infectious disease, and its frequency is less than 1% [1].

Observing this, it is possible to avoid injury to tissues, be sure to follow the rules for moving the removed organ into the container through an incision made with localization of the least thin abdominal wall, in combination with antibiotic prophylaxis. The development and implementation of the most modern techniques and technologies has made it possible to achieve a significant reduction in the number of cases of diseases in all groups of patients. The number of complications, according to studies conducted in 2000-2005 by S.A. Bychkov, was at the level of 2-5% among planned operations and 10-12% in urgent abdominal surgery. An almost tenfold decrease in the incidence of complications occurred by 2012-2015, that is, up to 0.5% in planned abdominal surgery in children and 1-2% in emergency laparoscopic abdominal surgery in children [13,16].

Over the past decades, contraindications and indications for the use of minimally invasive modern technologies in surgery in children have undergone significant changes, which served to maximize the expansion of these technologies. Previously, an absolute contraindication to laparoscopic surgery was the presence of scars on the anterior abdominal wall, due to previously performed laparotomic accesses during surgery, SCN, paresis of the small and large intestine, local or diffuse form of peritonitis, a fairly early age of children (newborn), hypotrophy and prematurity of

the child, as well as the detection of palpable formation in the abdominal cavities. To date, most of the above-mentioned contraindications are not absolute, while it should be noted that certain of them act as direct indications for performing diagnostic laparoscopy and further laparoscopic surgical treatment [9].

Now in modern medical works, you can find several definitions of the concept of "surgical risk". When used in the global surgical manual Sabiston Textbook of Surgery (2014), the concept of surgical risk means the sum of all possible risks associated with surgical intervention. The main risks that have a high prevalence are: the nature of the underlying surgical disease with its effect on homeostasis; the age of the patient; the method of anesthesia and its volume; the presence of concomitant pathologies, their nature, clinic; the volume of the operation; the obligation of intensive therapy in the postoperative period. The fundamental moment of a good result of surgical intervention in young children is the absence of unpleasant symptoms, complications caused not only by the operation, but also by concomitant diseases. Other risk factors subject to correction are the volume of the operation and the technique of execution [24,25,26].

The main rule of thumb for reducing the risk of surgical intervention is to minimize injury while protecting the patient as much as possible. As a rule, the volume of the operation is positively influenced by: tissue restriction, prevention of bleeding. It is advisable to propose the separation of all surgical interventions into low-, medium- and high-risk operations. Based on the literature data, for a quick determination of surgical risk, a comprehensive assessment of the patient's medical history and the results of laboratory and instrumental examination methods is important [12,14]

The main risks and possible complications of the use of endovideosurgical techniques in surgical interventions in children are currently widely discussed in the modern literature. Since there are recommendations for the prevention of diseases in the literature, the problem of forming a comprehensive therapeutic and preventive approach to each stage of patients' life, taking into account the specifics of the disease, remains insufficiently studied. That is why it is necessary to create algorithms for preoperative examination, intraoperative monitoring and postoperative management of the patient: only multidisciplinary interaction of surgeons, pediatricians, laboratory staff and doctors will ensure the optimal result of the child's treatment." - notes E.Y. Dyakonova (2018). Taking into account today's differences in surgical technique, antibiotic therapy does not significantly affect the further reduction in the number of intra-abdominal postoperative complications [17].

Also, despite the reports about the great advantages of laparoscopic access, the possibility of using this method is questioned by many scientists. Complicated appendicitis (acute acute appendicitis) tea is most often considered by specialists as a contraindication to laparoscopic appendectomy (LA). For children with appendicular peritonitis in the absence of pediatric surgical service and late hospitalization, the results of treatment remain problematic [3,21]. Due to the technological progress in surgical instruments, laparoscopic surgery is considered a standard procedure for most abdominal pathologies. Laparoscopy, as a minimally invasive method, has a number of advantages, which has validity and evidence in the works of many scientists [29].

The number of LA is growing significantly, while data were previously published that 66% of LA was performed with nonperforative appendicitis, now LA is used in 100% of cases [37]. M.G. Khirall, NI. Eldesouki, AA. Elzanaty, KA. Ismail, MA. Arafa (2017) believe that with the development and modernization of endoscopic technology, the possibilities of laparoscopic treatment are significantly expanded. They claim that laparoscopic surgery for appendicular peritonitis is widely used in their pediatric surgery center. It should be noted, for example, in Italy, LA is performed only in 47.3% of cases of appendicular peritonitis, and an increase in the number of postoperative intra-abdominal abscesses is reported, which may prevent the widespread introduction of LA as a standard procedure for complicated forms of acute appendicitis [11].

H. Ikeda, M. Aoki and A. Igarashi (2012) in their studies reported higher rates of postoperative intra-abdominal abscess in perforated appendicitis in children than in children with complicated appendicitis. Other researchers believe that LA should be performed with extreme caution in cases with the presence of appendicular infiltrate and peritonitis, due to the risk of bleeding and damage to internal organs [25,28]. After that, HK Chang, SJ Han, SH Choi (2013) published data on a high

frequency of switching to LA in the presence of severe adhesions or inflammation. According to SR Markar (2012), LA is technically easy to perform and has good postoperative results in children with uncomplicated appendicitis. In the last decade, when laparoscopy is becoming more common in surgical practice, there have been reports of successful LA in complicated appendicitis [20]

O.Z. Karakus, O. Ulusoy, O. Ateş (2016), according to their own observations, report that the timing of the development of intra-abdominal abscess after LA is variable. In general, there is a progressively increasing positive relationship between the development of a postoperative abscess and the maximum increase in body temperature on each subsequent day, which increases significantly after the third day. Most specialists wait up to 7 days after surgery to radiographically confirm or rule out the presence of an abscess. According to the meta-analysis of SR. Markar (2012), RM. Nataraja (2013) and S. Zhang (2017), devoted to acute complicated appendicitis in children, LA is associated with a high frequency of intra-abdominal abscesses in childhood. In this regard, doctors explain that pneumoperitoneum; inadequate peritoneal interception or unnecessary manipulations with an inflamed appendix are a possible cause of the spread of infection.

At the same time, an increase in surgical experience and skills in endovisular surgery undoubtedly contributes to an increase in the experience of doctors and a decrease in the frequency of complications. Thus, the data of Z.X. Low (2019) indicate that the average frequency of intra-abdominal abscess formation in children after LA reaches 7.94%, and with OA - 8.14%. Consequently, the results of the conducted LA are comparable with OA for this indicator [22]. Currently, it is possible to use reasonable tactics for the treatment of children, including measures to prevent the development and formation of adhesions. Thus, based on the data of the pathogenesis of adhesions, it became possible to prevent the formation and recurrence of cicatricial-adhesive changes in the abdominal cavity [8,19]. In order to prevent the appearance of the adhesive process in different periods of time, specialists have proposed a large number of different variations of drugs and solutions injected into the abdominal cavity in various forms [5,11,19]

"Good" surgical technique and the use of anti-adhesive agents are the main modern concepts of preventing adhesions [16]. Over the past ten years, there has been a rapid development and widespread introduction of endovideosurgical methods of treatment into abdominal surgical practice, which served as a hope for a decrease in the incidence of SCN [23]. Since all surgical interventions on the abdominal cavity are associated with peritoneal trauma and the risk of adhesions, the basis of measures necessary to prevent the formation of adhesions in the postoperative period in patients is both the elimination of the focus of inflammation, and the preservation and rapid restoration of the mesothelium of the damaged area of the peritoneum, sanitation of the abdominal cavity, as well as early rehabilitation and functioning of the gastrointestinal tract. These measures include systemic pharmacological agents and intraperitoneal drugs [10]

The mechanism of these drugs is based primarily on delineating the surfaces of damaged tissues during their regeneration and recovery, as well as the sliding of organs in relation to each other was unhindered. In addition, these measures lead to a decrease in the formation of fibrin, which is an unconditional formation of fusion [18].

References.

1. Almaramhy HH. Acute appendicitis in young children less than 5 years: review article. *Ital J Pediatr.* 2017;43(1):15. Published 2017 Jan 26.
2. Arung, W. Pathophysiology and prevention of postoperative peritoneal adhesions / W. Arung, M. Meurisse, O. Detry // *World J. Gastroenterol.* - 2011. - Vol. 17. - № 41. -pp. 4545-453.
3. Athanasiou C, Lockwood S, Markides GA. Systematic review and meta-analysis of laparoscopic versus open appendectomy in adults with complicated appendicitis: an update of the literature. *World J Surg.* 2017; 41:3083-99.
4. Bonadio W. Time to Appendectomy and Risk of Complicated Appendicitis and Adverse Outcomes in Children. *JAMA Pediatr.* 2018;172(1):94.

5. Chang HK, Han SJ, Choi SH, Oh J-T. Feasibility of a laparoscopic approach for generalized peritonitis from perforated appendicitis in children. *Yonsei Med J* 54:(2013)1478–1483
6. Clavien PA, Barkun J, de Oliveira ML, Vauthey JN, Dindo D, Schulick RD, de Santibañes E, Pekolj J, Slankamenac K, Bassi C, Graf R, Vonlanthen R, Padbury R, Cameron JL, Makuuchi M. The Clavien-Dindo classification of surgical complications: five-year experience. // *Ann Surg.*, 2009. Vol. 250, N 2. pp. 187 - 196.
7. Courtney M. Townsend, Jr., R. Daniel Beauchamp, B. Mark Evers, Kenneth L. Mattox. *Sabiston Textbook of Surgery*, 19th Edition. 2012.
8. Di Saverio S, Vennix S, Birindelli A, Weber D, Lombardi R, Mandrioli M, Tarasconi A, Bemelman WA. Pushing the envelope: laparoscopy and primary anastomosis are technically feasible in stable patients with Hinchey IV perforated acute diverticulitis and gross faeculent peritonitis. *Surg Endosc.* 2016 Dec;30(12):5656-64. doi: 10.1007/s00464-016-4869-y
9. Goussous N, Jenkins DH, Zielinski MD. Primary fascial closure after damage control laparotomy: sepsis vs haemorrhage. *Injury.* 2014 Jan;45(1):151-55. doi: 10.1016/j.injury.2013.01.039
10. Hope T. Jackson, Timothy D. Kane. Advances in Minimally Invasive Surgery in Pediatric Patients. *Advances in Pediatrics* 61 (2014) 149–195.
11. Ikeda H, Aoki M, Igarashi A, et al. *Masui.* 2012;61(9):925-931.
12. Jaschinski T., C. Mosch, M. Eikermann, E.A. Neugebauer. Laparoscopic versus open appendectomy in patients with suspected appendicitis: a systematic review of meta-analyses of randomised controlled trials. *BMC Gastroenterol.*, 15 (2015), p. 48
13. Karakuş OZ, Ulusoy O, Ateş O, Hakgüder G, Olguner M, Akgür FM (2016) Conventional single-port laparoscopic appendectomy for complicated appendicitis in children: Efficient and cost-effective. *J Minimal Access Surg* 12:16
14. Khirallah MG, Eldesouki NI, Elzanaty AA, Ismail KA, Arafa MA. Laparoscopic versus open appendectomy in children with complicated appendicitis. *Ann Pediatr Surg* 13(2017):17–20
15. Krielen P., Beukel B. A. van den, Stommel M. W. J. et al. In-hospital costs of an admission for adhesive small bowel obstruction // *World J. Emerg. Surg.* 2016. Vol. 11. P. 49. Doi: 10.1186/s13017-016-0109-y.
16. Low ZX, Bonney GK, So JBY, Loh DL, Ng JJ. Laparoscopic versus open appendectomy in pediatric patients with complicated appendicitis: a meta-analysis. *Surg Endosc.* 2019;33(12):4066–4077
17. Manegold BC, Schlicker H. [Endoscopy of the digestive tract in newborns. (In German).] *Fortschr Med.* 1982;100(8):328–331.
18. Maria E. Linnaus, Daniel J. Ostlie. Complications in common general pediatric surgery procedures. *Seminars in Pediatric Surgery* 25. 2016. 404–411.
19. Markar SR, Blackburn S, Cobb R, et al. Laparoscopic versus open appendectomy for complicated and uncomplicated appendicitis in children. *J Gastrointest Surg.* 2012; 16(10):1993-2004.
20. Masoomi H., N.T. Nguyen, M.O. Dolich, S. Mills, J.C. Carmichael, et al. Laparoscopic appendectomy trends and outcomes in the United States: data from the Nationwide Inpatient Sample (NIS), 2004-2011. *Am. Surg.*, 80 (2014), pp. 1074-1077
21. Powell RW. Stapled intestinal anastomosis in neonates and infants: use of the endoscopic intestinal stapler. *J Pediatr Surg.* 1995;30(2):195–197. doi: 10.1016/00223468(95)90559-6.
22. Rentea RM, Peter SD, Snyder CL. Pediatric appendicitis: state of the art review. *Pediatr Surg Int.* 2017;33(3):269–283. doi: 10.1007/s00383-016-3990-2.
23. Rentea RM, Peter SDS, Snyder CL. Pediatric appendicitis: state of the art review. *Pediatr Surg Int.* 2017;33(3):269–283.
24. Rentea RM, St Peter SD. Contemporary Management of Appendicitis in Children. *Adv Pediatr.* 2017;64(1):225–251.
25. Rentea RM, St Peter SD. Pediatric Appendicitis. *Surg Clin North Am.* 2017;97(1):93–112.

26. Salo M, Friman G, Stenström P, Ohlsson B, Arnbjörnsson E. Appendicitis in children: evaluation of the pediatric appendicitis score in younger and older children. *Surg Res Pract.* 2014; 2014:438076.
27. Sartelli M., Catena F., Ansaloni L., Moore E. Complicated intra-abdominal infections in a worldwide context: an observational prospective study (CIAOW Study) // *World Journal of Emergency Surgery.* - 2013. - Vol.8. - P. 1.
28. Seetahal SA, Bolorunduro OB, Sookdeo TC, et al. Negative appendectomy: a 10-year review of a nationally representative sample. *Am J Surg.* 2011;201(4):433–437. doi: 10.1016/j.amjsurg.2010.10.009.
29. Yeom S., M.S. Kim, S. Park, T. Son, Y.Y. Jung, et al. Comparison of the outcomes of laparoscopic and open approaches in the treatment of periappendiceal abscess diagnosed by radiologic investigation. *J. Laparoendosc. Adv. Surg. Tech. A*, 24 (2014), pp. 762-769

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

1 МАХСУС СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL
SPECIAL ISSUE 1

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000